

INTERLAMINAR SHEAR STRENGTH OF C-SiC BASED COMPOSITES REINFORCED WITH HEAT TREATED CARBON FIBERS

J. J. Sha^{1*}, J. X. Dai¹, Z. F. Zhang¹, J. Li¹, Z. Q. Wei¹, J.-M. Hausherr² and W. Krenkel²

¹ State Key Lab. of Structural Analyses for Industrial Equipment, Dalian University of Technology, Dalian, China

² Ceramic Materials Engineering, University of Bayreuth, Bayreuth D-95440, Germany

* Corresponding author (jjsha@dlut.edu.cn)

Keywords: *C-SiC based composite; heat treatment; interlaminar shear strength*

1. Introduction

Carbon fiber reinforced C-SiC based composites (C/C-SiC) are potential materials for the application of high-performance structures. Among many fabrication techniques for C/C-SiC composites, the liquid silicon infiltration (LSI) process is an attractive one because of its near-net shaping technique and good performance/cost benefits [1-4].

The manufacturing of C/C-SiC composites via the LSI process consists of three steps: (i) manufacturing of carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) green body; (ii) obtaining of porous C/C preform by converting polymer matrix into carbon at temperatures above 900 °C (carbonization step); (iii) fabrication of C/C-SiC composite through the liquid silicon infiltration into the C/C preform to form SiC matrix (siliconization step). At the different steps, the material shows a very different morphology. Especially, at the carbonization step, the shrinkage of the resin matrix caused by the evolution of gaseous products exhibiting a volume reduction of more than 50% is hindered by the stiff fiber. This leads to an extensive formation of network of both pores and cracks in the carbon matrix. During the siliconization step, the pores and cracks essentially act as the channel for the liquid silicon climbing into the inner parts being reacted with the carbon matrix or fiber to form the silicon carbide. Eventually, the matrix of C/C-SiC composites fabricated in such way includes amorphous carbon, silicon carbide and a small amount of residual silicon [2].

Based on the fabrication process described above, it is clear that the microstructure featured by the cracks/pores formed during the carbonization step has a significant effect on the phase composition of matrix and the properties of C/C-SiC composites. In general case, there are three different types of cracks

has been observed in the C/C preform, namely, transverse cracks which run through the fiber roving and divide it into three to five C/C segments, partial de-lamination cracks which normally occur at the interface between warp and weft fiber fabrics and the micro de-bonding cracks which appear at the fiber/matrix interface [5-6].

The mechanism for the formation of these cracks could be attributed to the interaction of fiber and matrix. Such interaction was caused by the stress generation due to the shrinkage of polymer matrix and hindering of stiff carbon fiber at the carbonization step. Obvious shrinkage normally occurred at temperature above 500 °C. The shrinkage of matrix would result in a tension stress in the matrix, and such tensile stress increases with rising the temperature. Under the tension stress, the site of the crack initiation is quite dependent on the interaction of fiber and matrix, where the fiber/matrix interface served as a medium. When the fiber/matrix bonding strength is larger than that of the matrix, the first cracks would initiate at the weakest site of matrix. Otherwise, the first crack would initiate at the interface of fiber and matrix being relaxed the tension stress. From which it could be seen that the formation and development of cracks are very sensitive to the fiber-matrix bonding strength [3,7]. This conclusion has also described in our previous work [8].

At the same time, it is well known that the surface activity of carbon fiber plays an important role on the fiber-matrix bonding strength [7-9]. The heat treatment of carbon fiber in inter gas atmosphere can reduce the fibers' surface activity. In other words, the change of fiber's surface activity can lead to a varied microstructure features of C/C preform, and

finally affect the phase composition and mechanical properties of C/C-SiC composites.

Therefore, in the current work, the carbon fibers were heat treated at elevated temperatures to investigate how the fiber treatment affecting the interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) of C/C-SiC composites by means of the double-notched shear (DNS) test. Furthermore, in order to clarify the mechanism for the change of ILSS: the surface activity of carbon fiber after treatment was analyzed by the X-ray Photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurement; the phase composition was identified by X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis; the surface morphologies before and after shear test were observed by optical microscope and scanning electron microscope (SEM), respectively.

2. Experimental procedure

2.1 Materials fabrication

Fig.1 shows the flow chart for the fabrication of C/C-SiC composites via LSI. Carbon fibers were heat treated in a graphitization furnace at temperatures ranging from 600 °C to 1500 °C in nitrogen atmosphere. Both the un-treated and treated carbon fibers were used as the reinforcement to fabricate the CFRP green body by resin transfer molding technique.

Fig. 1. The flow chart for the fabrication of C/C-SiC composites via liquid silicon infiltration (LSI) process.

Meanwhile, the surface composition of carbon fibers after treatment was measured by XPS, using a

spectrometer employing monochromatic and focused Al K α radiation.

Fig. 2 shows the image for the fabricated CFRP plates which are reinforced by the 2D carbon fiber fabrics treated at different temperatures.

Fig. 2. The image for the fabricated 2D CFRP plates reinforced with fibers treated at different temperatures

To obtain the C/C preform, the carbonization process was conducted in a graphitization furnace at temperatures above 1200 °C under vacuum. In order to remain the structure integrity of C/C preform during the carbonization, the heating rate should be low. Normally, it should be lower than 2 °C/min.

Fig. 3 shows the image for the C/C preform reinforced by carbon fibers treated at different temperatures. On a macro-scale level, in comparison to the CFRP green body, the obtained C/C preform has a clear volume shrinkage, and many cracks are visible in the carbon matrix. On micro-scale level, such C/C preform shows a cracked or porous structure. The details will be presented and discussed latter.

Fig. 3. The image for the C/C preform obtained by pyrolysis of the CFRP at temperature above 1200 °C

Siliconization was carried out by putting the C/C preform in a graphite crucible and embedding with the silicon powder at temperature above 1500 °C

under vacuum condition. Fig. 4 shows the image of fabricated C/C-SiC specimens reinforced with different carbon fibers. For some specimens, there are some solidified silicon drops sitting on the surface.

Fig. 4. The image for the C/C-SiC composites reinforced with fibers treated at different temperatures.

2.2 Measurement of interlaminar shear strength

The measurement of interlaminar shear strength was conducted on an Instron Universal Testing Machine (Model: 3345) by using the DNS test. The gauge length (the distance between two notches) of double-notched shear specimen is 6 mm. Fig. 5 shows the configuration, loading mode and geometric structure for the DNS test schematically.

Fig. 5. The geometric structure and jig configuration of DNS test.

The shape and dimension of the specimens were based on the testing standard C1425-05. The cross-

head speed and test temperature were 0.5 mm/min and 20 °C, respectively. For each condition, at least five specimens were tested. To calculate the interlaminar shear strength, ILSS, the following Eq. (1) was used:

$$ILSS = P / (w \cdot h) \tag{1}$$

where P is the maximum load (N), w is the specimen width (mm) and h is the distance between the notches (mm).

2.3 Observation of surface morphologies and fracture surface

For observing the surface morphologies, the samples were mounted in the resin for grinding and polishing. The mounted samples are initially ground by silicon carbide of grit size 300, 400 and 600, 1200 um, followed by alcoholic cleaning after each SiC grinding, then these were polished with a diamond paste up to 1 μm. After the sample is fine polished, it is dried to obtain scratch free morphology under optical microscope and scanning electron microscope.

3. Result and discussion

3.1 Surface composition of carbon fiber

Table 1 presents the surface composition of carbon fibers after heat treatment at different temperatures obtained by the XPS analysis.

As can be seen from table 1, the oxygen concentration on the surface of carbon fiber decreased with increasing the treatment temperature, but the carbon concentration increased with increasing the treatment temperature. The oxygen concentration is about 17.97% for un-treated fiber and 1.97% for 1500 °C heat treated fibers, respectively. The carbon concentration on the surface of fibers is 80.99% for un-treated fiber and 96.19 % for 1500 °C heated fiber, respectively.

Table1. The surface composition of carbon fibers treated at different temperatures.

Fiber	Atomic%			
	C(1s)	O(1s)	N(1s)	Si(2p)
Un-treated fiber	80.99	17.79	0.48	0.32
Treated at 900°C	94.04	3.65	1.91	0.2
Treated at 1500°C	96.19	1.97	0.78	0.31

It has been known that the oxygen-containing function groups play an important role on the fiber/matrix bonding [9]. Thus, the atomic ratio of O(1s)/C(1s) was calculated by using the data in table 1. The O/C atomic ratio is the highest for the untreated fibers which is 21.97%, while fibers treated at 1500 °C show the smallest O (1s)/C (1s) ratio with a value of 2.05%, from which it can be seen that the O/C ratio decreases with increasing the treatment temperature. Consequently, the activity of carbon fiber's surface decreased with increasing the heat treatment temperature. In our previous work, the fiber/matrix bonding strength at the CFRP step has been measured [8]. Result found that the CFRP reinforced with un-treated fiber has a much higher fiber/matrix bonding strength than that of 1500 °C treated fiber-reinforced one. The fiber/matrix bonding strength has a strong influence on the microstructure evolution of CFRP during the carbonization step as described in section 3.3.

3.2 Morphologies of CFRP

Fig. 6 shows the morphologies of 2D carbon fiber fabrics reinforced CFRP observed by optical microscope.

Fig. 6. The morphologies of CFRP: (a) reinforced with un-treated carbon fibers; (b) reinforced with 1500 °C treated carbon fibers.

It is clear that the carbon fibers are uniformly embedded in the phenolic resin matrix in both un-treated and 1500 °C treated fiber fabrics reinforced plates. Almost no cracks were observed in the un-treated fiber fabrics reinforced laminate as shown in Fig. 6(a). In contrast, some tiny cracks caused by fiber-matrix interface de-bonding, appeared in the plates reinforced with fiber fabrics treated at temperature of 1500 °C as shown in Fig. 6(b). Such de-bonding cracks might be formed during the cooling down from post-curing temperature, and could be attributed to the weak fiber/matrix interface bonding caused by fiber treatment.

3.3 Morphologies of C/C preform

The C/C preform was obtained by the carbonization of CFRP green body above 1200 °C. Due to the CFRP green bodies were reinforced with fibers treated at different temperatures, thus, the carbonization of different CFRP can obtain the C/C preform with variable microstructure features.

Fig. 7 shows the morphologies for the un-treated and 1500 °C treated fibers reinforced C/C preform. A clear difference could be observed.

Fig. 7. The morphologies of C/C preform: (a) reinforced with un-treated carbon fibers; (b) reinforced with 1500 °C treated carbon fibers.

For the C/C preform reinforced with the untreated fibers, the fiber/matrix bonding strength is high resulting a strong interaction of fiber and matrix. In this case, the main crack types are transverse cracks and micro-delamination cracks as shown in Fig. 7(a). For the C/C preform reinforced with 1500 °C treated fibers, as a result of weak interaction of fiber and matrix, the main crack type is micro-cracks caused by fiber-matrix de-bonding as shown in Fig. 7(b). Because the small crack size, it shows a porous structure.

The mechanism for different morphologies can be well illustrated in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. The schematic illustration of the microstructure evolution during the carbonization step.

Based on the TG data, it has been known that the obvious carbonization of resin matrix starts at temperature above 500 °C [8]. Thus, when the pyrolysis temperature exceeds 500 °C, the significant shrinkage of resin matrix occurred being gradually converted to a gassy carbon. In comparison to the converting matrix, the carbon fiber has a very low coefficient of thermal expansion along the fiber axis [10]. In this case, the shrinkage of matrix would be hindered by the stiff carbon fiber, resulting in a tensile stress in the matrix. Based on the definition of fiber bundle and the analysis of stress state in Fig. 8, we can see that the 90° fiber bundle is in tension state, but in compression state for 0° fiber bundle.

Once the tensile stress exceeds the matrix strength or fiber/matrix bonding strength locally, the cracks would be initiated at the weakest site of matrix or interface of fiber/matrix. Therefore, the type of cracks is dependent on the comparison between matrix strength and fiber/matrix bonding strength. For the un-treated fiber reinforced composite, due to a high fiber/matrix bonding

strength, firstly the tensile stress would exceed the tensile strength of the resin matrix, transverse cracks and micro-delamination cracks are preferentially formed in the 90° fiber-matrix region or at the interface between 0° and 90° fiber layer. Meanwhile, the 90° fiber-matrix regions were separated into some individual C/C segments being accompanied with micro-delamination cracks as shown in Fig. 7(a). In contrast, the composite reinforced with 1500 °C treated fibers, the fiber/matrix bonding strength is low, and the tensile stress would result in the micro-debonding cracks. Such micro-debonding cracks are mainly appeared at the interface between fiber and matrix leading to porous structure as shown in Fig. 7(b).

3.4 Morphologies of C/C-SiC composites

The C/C-SiC composites were fabricated by infiltrating the liquid silicon into the C/C preform at temperature beyond 1450 °C. Fig. 9 shows the morphologies of C/C-SiC composite manufactured by the technique presented in Fig.1. It is obvious that the liquid silicon enters the C/C preform through the micro-cracks/pores formed during the carbonization step of CFRP, being reacted with the adjacent C phase to form the SiC matrix.

Fig. 9 Optical microscope observation of surface morphologies of C/C-SiC composites, (a): reinforced with un-treated fibers; (b): reinforced with 1500 °C treated fibers.

In Fig. 9, the regions with different colours represent the different matrix composition. The dark phase is carbon matrix/fiber; the gray phase is the SiC matrix and the white is the residual Si. However, the morphologies for the C/C-SiC composites reinforced with fibers treated at different temperatures are quite different. For the un-treated fiber reinforced composite as shown in Fig. 9(a), the distribution zone of SiC matrix is regular and mainly in the stripe-like transverse regions, which separated the 90 ° fiber bundle into some C/C segments. As for the composite reinforced with fibers treated at 1500 °C, the carbon fibers were surrounded by the SiC matrix as shown in Fig. 9(b). In other words, the distribution zone of SiC in C/C-SiC composite is very similar to the crack pattern as observed in Fig. 7.

The phase composition was further confirmed by the XRD analysis. Fig. 10 shows the XRD diffraction patterns for the composites reinforced with fibers treated at different temperatures.

Fig. 10. XRD patterns of C/C-SiC composites

The consisting phases in un-treated fiber-reinforced C/C-SiC composites mainly included carbon and SiC. The carbon peak should be produced by the carbon fiber. The SiC was formed by the reaction of infiltrated liquid silicon with the carbon matrix and fiber. And also, a silicon peak was also found. As for the 1500 °C treated fiber-reinforced C/C-SiC composite, the intensity of SiC peak is much higher than that of un-treated fiber-

reinforced one, and there is almost no residual silicon existing.

From the analysis of crack type in C/C preform and phase composition in C/C-SiC composites, it can be concluded that the crack type is a dominant factor not only for the distribution and volume fraction of SiC phase, but also for the consisting phase in final product of C/C-SiC composite.

Based on the reaction mechanism governing the siliconization of porous C/C preform in the literatures [11-13], it was inferred that the initial formation of SiC layer was very fast and the formed SiC precipitated on the wall of channel being acted as the barrier for the further contact of silicon and carbon. Therefore, the subsequent growth of SiC layer is controlled by diffusion of silicon through the SiC layer. Meanwhile, the capillary radius would decrease with increasing the infiltration time. The crack width in the un-treated fiber-reinforced C/C preform is large as shown in Fig. 7(a). The liquid silicon climbing into such cracks by capillary force has a large volume fraction. When the first SiC layer is formed on the wall, the reaction rate of silicon located at the center of cracks with carbon was low and mainly controlled by the diffusion. That would result in the existence of residual silicon. The C/C preform reinforced with 1500 °C treated fibers shows a porous microstructure and the crack/pore size is small as shown in Fig. 7(b). The volume fraction of infiltrated silicon in each crack or pore is small and could completely contact with the fresh carbon to form the SiC. Because the volume fraction of crack/pore is high in 1500 °C treated fiber-reinforced C/C preform, finally, the SiC content in the matrix is also high and the quantity of residual silicon is very limited as shown in Fig. 10.

3.5 ILSS of C/C-SiC composites

Fig. 11 shows the macroscopic image of C/C-SiC composites before and after DNS tests under the compressive loading. The image indicates that the interlaminar shear failure occurred along the desired plane which is perpendicular to the two notch tips. The shear fractured surface is parallel to the loading direction. For the successfully tested specimens, they failed in the similar way. By using the ultimate load recorded in the load-displacement curves and the Eq. (1), the ILSS can be determined as shown in Fig. 12.

Fig. 12 shows the interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) of 2D C/C-SiC composites as a function of heat treatment temperature. It is clear that the ILSS increased with increasing the heat treatment temperature. The ILSS for the un-treated fiber reinforced composite is about 22.8 Mpa. After heat treatment at 1500 °C, the ILSS reaches to 34 Mpa, which increased by 33% in comparison to that of the un-treated one. For understanding the mechanism of improved ILSS, the morphologies of interlaminar shear fractured surface were observed by SEM.

Fig. 11. The microscopic image for the DNS specimens before and after test.

Fig. 12. The interlaminar shear strength as a function of heat treatment temperature.

Fig.13 shows the fractured surface morphologies of C/C-SiC composites reinforced with 1500 °C treated fibers. The main features of specimens reinforced with fibers treated at other temperatures are similar to those in Fig. 13 (a).

Under the compressive loading, the shear stress would be concentrated in the sharp locations of inner defects and the notch tips. The cracks would be firstly initiated at such locations and then propagated in the matrix or along the fiber/matrix interface [17].

From the Fig. 13(a), it can be seen that the fracture surface mainly consists of three distinct zones (defined as zone A, B and C). The details for each zone are shown in Fig. 13(b)-(d) which are corresponding to the zone A, B and C.

Fig. 13. Morphologies of shear fractured surface for the 2D C/C-SiC reinforced with 1500°C heat treated fibers.

However, the relative area of three different zone in C/C-SiC composite reinforced with fibers treated at different temperature is different. The fractured matrix occupied relative larger area. The difference in the fractured surface among composites reinforced with fibers treated at different temperature could be associated with the volume fraction of SiC phase and its distribution as well as the change of fiber/matrix bonding strength.

The ILSS was mainly determined by the matrix strength and fiber/matrix bonding strength. The large volume fraction of SiC phase and its homogeneous distribution could increase the matrix strength and fiber/matrix bonding strength, consequently, improving the structure integrity and reducing the stress concentration. Under the interlaminar shear loading, the generated cracks could change their propagation direction when they meet the interface. As a result, ILSS increases with increasing fiber

treatment temperature. The improved fiber/matrix bonding strength means that the cracks had larger opportunity to propagate in the matrix rather than along the interface. Therefore, the fractured matrix occupied relative larger area in the fractured surface for the composites reinforced with fibers treated at a higher temperature. The deflection of the crack can be seen in Fig. 13(b). Fig. 13(c) shows the transition zone from the cracked matrix zone to fiber/matrix de-bonding zone. When the crack propagated from the matrix to the fiber/matrix interface, some of fibers broke by shear loading when the orientation of spreading fiber was not parallel to the crack propagation direction. The fiber breaking is mainly caused by the strong fiber/matrix bonding as shown in Fig. 13(d).

4 Summary

C/C-SiC composites by liquid silicon infiltration (LSI) process are potential materials for the applications of high temperature technologies. However, the microstructure and phase composition of C/C-SiC composites are closely associated with the microstructure features of C/C perform produced at the intermediate step, which are mainly controlled by the fiber/matrix bonding strength at the CFRP step. In the current work, in order to fabricate the C/C-SiC composites with varied microstructure and morphologies, the fiber/matrix bonding strength at the CFRP step was modified by the heat treatment of carbon fiber. The main results are summarized as follows:

(1) The heat treatment of carbon fiber could effectively change the consisting phases and their distribution in the matrix of C/C-SiC composites. The morphologies for the C/C-SiC composites reinforced with fibers treated at different temperatures are quite different. For the composite reinforced with fibers treated at 1500 °C, a high volume fraction and homogeneous distribution of SiC phase were obtained. And the content of residual silicon was minimized.

(2) The ILSS for the un-treated fiber reinforced composite is about 22.8 Mpa. After heat treatment at 1500°C, the ILSS reaches to 34 Mpa, which increased by 33% in comparison to that of the un-treated one. Combing the ILSS result with the microstructure analysis, it can be concluded that the

high ILLS after heat treatment of carbon fiber could be attributed to a more homogeneous distribution of SiC phase and a strong fiber/matrix bonding.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by National Nature Science Foundation of China (grant no.: 50820145202), the Fundamental Research Funds for the Central Universities (grant no.: DUT11ZD (G) 01) and the Program for New Century Excellent Talents in University of Ministry of Education of China.

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